

STRATEGIES AND APPROACHES IN TEACHING VALUES EDUCATION AMONG PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOL

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Abstract

Values Education functions become as an agent in socialization and the need to help students grow to possess more highly developed moral standards, and it is also recognized as an integral part of the teacher's roles as well. This research aimed to determine the strategies and approaches in teaching values education among public secondary school in the Division of Zambales, utilizing the quantitative descriptive-survey research design with questionnaire as the main instrument in gathering data from the population of 300 values educational teachers. The findings showed that Values Education teachers always used Inculcation Approach as strategy in teaching; they are strongly agreed that the strategies in teaching Values Education was the most difficult dimension in teaching Values Education; there is significant differences on age and religious affiliation towards inculcation approach and significant on age towards Awareness Approach; there is a significant difference on age towards difficulty on contents; however, there is a negligible relationship between the academic performance and the strategies and approaches, as well as, the difficulties in teaching values education.

Keywords: Values Education, Teaching Strategies and Approaches, Secondary School, Training Design.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of Values Education in education is no longer new to our age. Written records will tell that from the time of Aristotle and the bible to at present time, state that great teachers are instrumental in conveying values teachings to the students. Values Education functions become as agent in socialization and the need to help students grow to possess more highly developed moral standards. "As a twig is bent, so the tree will grow" as William Wordsworth said. There is abundant rationale for the environment of public education in the values education training of students. Many researchers and learning theorist like John Dewey, Jean Piaget and Lawrence Kohlberg believed that the responsibility for the values development of the child falls upon the schools. All formal education should include values education, the school should be a place where the activity of each individual can also be social in character, where the students can develop as an individual and at the same time use his powers to further the larger activities of the group. It is the moral responsibility of the teacher to supply every possible aid to this process. The goal of values education in the school is to help young students become ethically mature adults, capable of moral thought and action (Ryan, 2016).

Character development is another term used in the place of values education. To develop one's character is to train one to exhibit certain traits that desirable one's character on the stage of life. Values education is a term often used interchangeably with moral teaching by teachers. A value is a belief that is intrinsically valuable or desirable to any individual. Value classification approach to moral education portrayed values in the following manner that persons have experiences. They grow and learn out of experiences that may come certain general guides to

behavior. These guides tend to give direction to life and are called values. Our values show what we tend to do with our limited time and energy. Meanwhile a moral belief may have value to the individual but that value is based upon rightness or wrongness of the belief producing an action. Values education can take place in any situation or institutions. Dealing with values is recognized as an integral part of teacher's roles. Education has an enormous role to play in the social, intellectual and political transformation. Thus, it is important to equip students with certain values starting from basic education. The students can use these and reflect them in their own behavior. Hence, this research will be conducted to find out if the students have learned core values especially during this pandemic time when students will be learning thru online teaching and distance modular teaching. Their honesty, responsibility, respect, hard work will be seen from their actions and activity.

Statement of the Problem

The research aimed to determine the strategies and approaches in teaching values education among public secondary school in the Division of Zambales.

Specifically, the study is guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Sex;
 - 1.3. Years in teaching Values Education;
 - 1.4. Number of training or seminars attended in values education;
 - 1.5. Religious Affiliation; and
 - 1.6. Civil Status?
2. How do the teachers use the strategies in teaching values education in terms of:
 - 2.1. Inculcation Approach;
 - 2.2. Awareness Approach;
 - 2.3. Moral Reasoning Approach;
 - 2.4. Value Clarification Approach; and
 - 2.5. Evocation Approach?
3. How effective are the strategies and approaches in teaching Values Education in terms of:
 - 3.1. Inculcation Approach;
 - 3.2. Awareness Approach;
 - 3.3. Moral Reasoning Approach;
 - 3.4. Value Clarification Approach; and
 - 3.5. Evocation Approach?

4. How are the difficulties in teaching values education be described by the teachers in terms of:
 - 4.1. Content/teaching domains;
 - 4.2. Strategy; and
 - 4.3. Assessment?
5. How is the academic performance of the Junior High School Students in Values Education be described?
6. Is there significant differences on the use of strategies and approaches in teaching values education when grouped according to profile variables?
7. Is there significant differences on the difficulties in teaching values education as described by the teachers when grouped according to profile variables?
8. Is there a significant relationship on the use and effectiveness of strategies and approaches in teaching values education to the academic performance of the students?
9. Is there a significant relationship on the difficulties in teaching values education as described by the teachers and the academic performance of the students?

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Legal Basis on the Teaching of Values Education

Values Education as a part of the school curriculum is the process by which values are formed in the learner under the guidance of the teacher and as he interacts with this environment. Legal bases of education were made for the common good of the learners, teachers, and other people involved in the education system. It is like a guiding star that help teachers find the right path that they must follow so that they can achieved the objectives of education.

In the Philippines, education is a public or state function. Public elementary and secondary education is supported by the national government, the former as mandated by the Constitution (1987), which states that “That state shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all level and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all, and he latter by Republic Act No. 6655 (Free Secondary Education Act). Specific provisions on education upon which all decrees, policies, regulations and rules on education are based, are provided in the Constitutions. These are expressly stated by a way of the constitutional mandate, Presidential decree and other legal provisions. The objective of formal education at the elementary, secondary, and tertiary levels as well as those of non-formal education are specified in the Education Act of 1982. The Republic Act No. 6728 deals with private education, notable by setting common minimum physical facilities and curricular requirement for all schools and by liberalizing content of values education. In August 2001, Republic Act No. 9155, otherwise called the Governance of Basic Education Act, was passed transforming the name of the Department of Education, Culture and Sports (DECS) to the Department of Education (DepEd) and redefining the role of field offices (regional offices, division offices,

district offices and schools). This Act provides the overall framework for; (i) school heads empowerment by strengthening their leadership roles; (ii) school-based management within the context of transparency and local accountability. The goals of basic education is to provide the school age population and young adults with skills, knowledge and values to become caring, self-reliant, productive and patriotic citizens.

Concept of Values Education

Since every person belongs to the family of humanity certain basic values which are accepted universally. Without these basic values the character would be lacking in certain primary traits. The basic value are essential to profound a character just like the foundation to the building. Without foundation the building would not stand, so also without basic values we cannot build a sound character. Education has a fundamental role to play in personal and social development. Values education should become the corner stone of the educational system and moral upliftment of younger generation. On one hand it is the need of the hour and on the other hand the edifice of educational reconstruction to build up individual personality with all good and possible values attached to it (Chaitanya, 2017).

Values education does not mean value imposition or value indoctrination. Value education teaches us to preserve what is good and worthwhile in what we have inherited form our culture Value education has capacity to transform a diseased mind into a fresh, young, innocent healthy natural and attentive mind. The transformed mind is capable of higher sensitivity and heightened level of perception. It helps us to accept respect the attitude and behavior of those who differ from us. The term values is often used to refer to the principles and beliefs which act as general guides to behavior and enable the individual to judge what is desirable and what is not. It is necessary to teach values in the formative years and no child is born with such knowledge. The phrase 'Values Education' as used in the area of school education refers to the study of development of essential values in pupils and the practices suggested for the promotion of the same. In its full range of meaning, value education includes developing the appropriate sensibilities moral, cultural, spiritual and the ability to make proper value judgment and internalize them in one's life. It is an education for 'becoming' and involves the total personality of the individual. Value education is essentially 'Man Making' and 'Character Building' (Chaitanya, 2017).

METHODOLOGY

The study employed descriptive research method with the survey questionnaire and interview guides as the research instruments. This type of research method includes proper analyses, interpretation, comparisons, identification, trends and relationship. The study assessed the perception of teachers on the on the determinants and effectiveness of strategies and approaches in teaching values education. The study employed survey method using a closed-ended questionnaire in gathering the data from the 300 Values Education teachers in public secondary schools in the Division of Zambales. The profile variables of the respondents was determined using the frequency and percentage distribution; the mean analysis was conducted to determine the teaching strategies and approaches, and difficulties in teaching values education, guided by

a 4-point Likert scale, 4 as the highest and 1 as the lowest; the Analysis of Variance was likewise done to compare the means to determine significant differences of the respondents' perception and responses when group according to profile variables, where, Reject the null hypothesis if $p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$ and Accept the null hypothesis if $p\text{-value} \geq 0.05$. Test of correlation was also conducted to test whether teaching strategies and approaches in values education has significant relationship with the students' academic performance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Profile Variables of the Respondents

Table 1: Profile Variables of the Respondents

Profile of the Respondents		Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Sex	Male	93	31.00
	Female	207	69.00
	Total	300	100.00
Age Mean=36.53 years old	51 above	25	8.30
	46-50 years old	25	8.30
	41-45 years old	40	13.30
	36-40 years old	65	21.70
	31-35 years old	73	24.30
	21-30 years old	72	24.00
	Total	300	100.00
Years in Teaching Values Education Mean=6.95 years	1-5 years	158	52.70
	11-15 years	21	7.00
	6-10 years	92	30.70
	16-20 years	13	4.30
	21 and above	16	5.30
	Total	300	100.00
No. of trainings in Moral Education/Values Education Mean=4.89 or 5	15 trainings and above	16	5.30
	10-14 trainings	15	5.00
	5-9 trainings	44	14.70
	1-4 trainings	225	75.00
	Total	300	100.00
Religious Affiliation	Roman Catholic	192	64.00
	Iglesia ni Cristo	42	14.00
	Baptist	11	3.70
	Protestant	9	3.00
	Born Again	43	14.30
	Islam	3	1.00
Civil Status	Single	103	34.30
	Widow	13	4.30
	Divorced	15	5.00
	Married	160	53.30
	Separated	9	3.00
	Total	300	100.00

Majority are female with 207 or equivalent to 69.00% while 93 or 31.00% are males. The data clearly manifest on the superiority of the female teacher-respondents compared to male and this could be ascribed of the innate-patience characteristics of females. Most of the teacher-respondents are from age group of 31-35 years old with 73 or 24.30%. The computed mean age of the teacher-respondents was 36.53 years old. Majority of the teacher-respondents had been teaching values education for 1-5 years with 158 or 52.70%. The computed mean years in teaching values education was 6.95 years. Majority of the teacher-respondents had attended 1-14 trainings with 225 or 75.00%. The computed mean number of trainings attended in moral education was 4.89 or 5 trainings. Majority of the teacher-respondents are affiliated in the Roman Catholic with 192 or equivalent to 64.00%. The data clearly illustrates on the dominance of the respondents as member of the Roman Catholic religion and this could be ascribed on the existence of the religion in the Philippines for almost five hundred (500) years. Majority of the teacher-respondents are married with 160 or equivalent to 53.30%. The data simply implies on the readiness of the values education teacher-respondents in handling marital responsibility.

Assessment on the Use of Strategies and Approaches and its Effectiveness in Teaching Values Education

Table 2: Use of Strategies and Approaches and its Effectiveness in Teaching Values Education in terms of Inculcation Approach

Inculcation Approach	Usage			Effectiveness		
	Mean	QI	Rank	Mean	QI	Rank
1. Teacher conducts various curricular activities related to values formation	3.54	Always	7.5	3.48	Very Much Effective	9.5
2. Teacher uses different approaches inclusive of using storytelling and story writing that portrays values development in life	3.55	Always	5.5	3.51	Very Much Effective	3.5
3. Teacher uses advertisements like collecting stamp, workshops and writing diary that helps students to some tasks to become responsible students.	3.40	Always	10	3.49	Very Much Effective	7.5
4. Teacher uses prayers and meditation as motivation.	3.50	Always	9	3.53	Very Much Effective	1
5. Teacher teaches love of nature, responsibility and protection.	3.64	Always	2	3.49	Very Much Effective	7.5
6. Teacher encourages participation, self-control national consciousness.	3.67	Always	1	3.51	Very Much Effective	3.5
7. Teacher emphasizes the value of hard work, service and dutifulness.	3.60	Always	3	3.51	Very Much Effective	3.5
8. Teacher develops sportsmanship, team spirit and tolerance.	3.55	Always	5.5	3.50	Very Much Effective	6
9. Teacher develops value consciousness through story by giving certain points about the cause and effect.	3.54	Always	7.5	3.51	Very Much Effective	3.5
10. Teacher paves the way for thinking skills approach because experiences response stimulates students to discuss issues at a deep level.	3.58	Always	4	3.48	Very Much Effective	9.5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.56	Always		3.50	Very Much Effective	

The overall weighted mean on the use of strategies and approaches in teaching Values Education in terms of Inculcation Approach was 3.56 “Always”, and 3.50 “Very Much Effective”. The teachers of the present study always use Inculcation Approach in teaching Values Education primarily for the purpose of encouraging the students to participate (e.g., civic duties and social responsibilities), to develop self-control and national consciousness. The result also signifies that inculcation approach is well used inside the classroom wherein teacher/s forced the students to act according to specific desired values.

Table 3: Strategies and Approaches in Teaching Values Education in terms of Awareness Approach

Awareness Approach	Usage			Effectiveness		
	Mean	QI	Rank	Mean	QI	Rank
1. The teacher enhances students’ awareness and identify their own values.	3.57	Always	1	3.44	Very Much Effective	6.5
2. The teacher encourages students to share their experiences that demonstrates desirable values	3.55	Always	2.5	3.45	Very Much Effective	3.5
3. The teacher presents value laden situation, readings and films about values thoughts, feelings, belief and behavior.	3.50	Always	4.5	3.44	Very Much Effective	6.5
4. The teacher uses role playing, group dynamics and simulations in training students to develop appropriate behavior, character and attitudes.	3.47	Always	9.5	3.46	Very Much Effective	2
5. The teacher engages students in the process of making inferences, analysis, making decision and finding solutions.	3.47	Always	9.5	3.43	Very Much Effective	9
6. Teacher guides and helps students to be open-minded, develop wider perspective in life and to have self-direction.	3.50	Always	4.5	3.45	Very Much Effective	3.5
7. Teacher demonstrates ways to identify and discourage peer abuse.	3.49	Always	7	3.46	Very Much Effective	1
8. Teacher promotes special habits that help student work together harmoniously.	3.49	Always	7	3.44	Very Much Effective	6.5
9. Teacher encourages students to participate in activities, program and processes that promote respect, understanding and peace among co-students.	3.49	Always	7	3.42	Very Much Effective	10
10. Teacher consistently explains to the students how the core values help them make good choices.	3.55	Always	2.5	3.44	Very Much Effective	6.5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.51	Always		3.44	Very Much Effective	

The overall weighted mean on the use of Strategies and Approaches in Teaching Values Education in terms of Awareness Approach was 3.56 “Always”; and 3.44 “Very Much Effective”. The teachers of the present study always use Awareness Approach in teaching Values Education aimed for enhancing students’ awareness and identify their own values. The

result also signifies that the respondents always utilize awareness approach which allows students to better engage themselves in the process of making inferences about values from the thoughts, feelings, beliefs or behavior of themselves and others.

Table 4: Strategies and Approaches in Teaching Values Education in terms of Moral Reasoning Approach

Moral Reasoning Approach	Usage			Effectiveness		
	Mean	QI	Rank	Mean	QI	Rank
1. The teacher sets up learning experiences which will facilitate and ensure moral development.	3.57	Always	1	3.46	Very Much Effective	9
2. The teacher serves as moral example in relation to the moral development of students.	3.56	Always	2.5	3.47	Very Much Effective	6.5
3. The teacher sees students delivering and reasoning power to attain higher level of learning.	3.52	Always	9.5	3.49	Very Much Effective	3
4. The teacher teaches students to develop appropriate personal values, group values and societal values.	3.53	Always	7.5	3.49	Very Much Effective	3
5. The teacher uses instructional at the classroom level and on the learning activities of students.	3.53	Always	7.5	3.46	Very Much Effective	9
6. Teacher inculcates core and ethical Filipino values.	3.56	Always	2.5	3.48	Very Much Effective	4.5
7. Teacher enriches understanding of moral development within the framework of everyday life.	3.52	Always	9.5	3.46	Very Much Effective	9
8. Teacher develops moral reasoning patterns that urge students to value choices.	3.54	Always	6	3.48	Very Much Effective	4.5
9. Teacher is happy teaching moral values, work ethics with full spirit.	3.55	Always	4.5	3.49	Very Much Effective	3
10. Teacher enriches student moral by seeing this behavior in School.	3.55	Always	4.5	3.47	Very Much Effective	6.5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.54	Always		3.47	Very Much Effective	

The overall weighted mean on the use of Strategies and Approaches in Teaching Values Education as to Moral Reasoning Approach was 3.54 “Always”; and 3.47 “Very Much Effective”. The teachers of the present study always use Awareness Approach in teaching Values Education aimed for setting up learning experiences which will facilitate and ensure moral development. The teacher-respondents always utilized the setting up of classroom activities for learning experiences which will facilitate and ensure moral development (e.g., core and ethical Filipino values, moral values, work ethics with full spirit).

Table 5: Strategies and Approaches in Teaching Values Education in terms of Value Clarification Approach

Value Clarification Approach	Usage			Effectiveness		
	Mean	QI	Rank	Mean	QI	Rank
1. Teacher sees to it that every learner is given attention and don't show partiality.	3.49	Always	9.5	3.47	Very Much Effective	1
2. Teacher feels attached to their student and give recognition to the individual potentiality on rewards from a good job.	3.50	Always	6.5	3.41	Very Much Effective	9
3. Teacher is given free support from the administration in all activities in relation to values education. .	3.50	Always	6.5	3.43	Very Much Effective	7
4. Teacher helps students to use logical thinking.	3.52	Always	3.5	3.43	Very Much Effective	7
5. Teacher recognizes individual learners as a rational being that can attain the highest good.	3.52	Always	3.5	3.44	Very Much Effective	4
6. Teacher develops the skills among learners relevant to making value judgment.	3.54	Always	1	3.45	Very Much Effective	2
7. Teacher's teaching strategies reform the students and help them to become better citizen.	3.52	Always	3.5	3.39	Very Much Effective	10
8. Teacher enforces innovative changes in the teaching learning process.	3.52	Always	3.5	3.43	Very Much Effective	7
9. Teacher uses psychological approach adopted for the development of the students.	3.49	Always	9.5	3.44	Very Much Effective	4
10. Teacher develops high level of consciousness, spiritual upliftment and self-actualization among the learner to become fully assets of the society	3.50	Always	6.5	3.44	Very Much Effective	4
Overall Weighted Mean	3.51	Always		3.43	Very Much Effective	

The overall weighted mean on the use of Strategies and Approaches in Teaching Values Education as to Value Clarification Approach was 3.51 “Always”; and 3.43 “Very Much Effective. The teachers of the present study always utilize Awareness Approach in teaching Values Education lessons with the primary aim to develop among students/learners the capability to make value judgment which are relevant and purposeful.

Lessons in Values Education were focused on helping the students to use logical thinking; recognized that they are rational being capable of doing good with themselves and others; and become better citizen of the community and country as a whole.

Table 6: Strategies and Approaches in Teaching Values Education in terms of Evocation Approach

Evocation Approach	Usage			Effectiveness		
	Mean	QI	Rank	Mean	QI	Rank
1. The teacher allows and guides students to appropriately speak their mind and express their emotions.	3.49	Always	3	3.45	Very Much Effective	3
2. The teacher provides a provocative situation for which spontaneous reactions are elicited.	3.50	Always	1	3.40	Very Much Effective	8.5
3. The teacher encourages their students to make spontaneously free, how rational choices.	3.48	Always	5	3.40	Very Much Effective	8.5
4. The teacher encourages students to make acceptable reactions and body gestures to a certain situation or scenario	3.47	Always	7	3.41	Very Much Effective	7
5. The teacher uses online instructional videos on how to manage emotions.	3.46	Always	9.5	3.37	Very Much Effective	10
6. Teacher sees to it that every student is given attention and do not show partiality.	3.47	Always	7	3.43	Very Much Effective	4.5
7. Teacher is given full support from the administration in all activities in relation to moral education.	3.49	Always	3	3.43	Very Much Effective	4.5
8. Teacher gives recognition to individual students' potentiality.	3.49	Always	3	3.47	Very Much Effective	2
9. Teacher implements a rational consciousness on issues about moral and values in the society.	3.47	Always	7	3.48	Very Much Effective	1
10. Teacher enforces the needs to discuss moral dilemmas in activities related to values formation and education.	3.46	Always	9.5	3.42	Very Much Effective	6
Overall Weighted Mean	3.48	Always		3.43	Very Much Effective	

The overall weighted mean on the use of Strategies and Approaches in Teaching Values Education as to Evocation Approach was 3.48 “Always”; and 3.43 “Very Much Effectiveness. The teacher-respondents always utilized in their teaching of Values Education lessons the Evocation Approach primarily providing a provocative situation for which spontaneous reactions are elicited.

Assessment of the Difficulties in Teaching Values Education

Table 7: Difficulties in Teaching Values Education in terms of Content/Teaching Domain

Context/Teaching Domains	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Rank
1. Limited highlights on the importance of teacher's knowledge and understanding of learners characteristics and experiences	3.35	Strongly Agree	9
2. Limited understanding on Kto12 curriculum being culture responsive, integrative and contextualized, relevant and responsive.	3.38	Strongly Agree	5
3. Limited discussion on diversity that emanates from factors such as gender, religious beliefs, family values and practices	3.43	Strongly Agree	2
4. Limited learning activities aimed to develop students' personal values, group values and societal values	3.45	Strongly Agree	1
5. Inadequate attention on the importance of renewed emphasis on citizenship, growing nationalism and environmental awareness	3.39	Strongly Agree	3
6. Ethical issues about students' rights of choice in regard to values formation.	3.38	Strongly Agree	5
7. Teachers have limited in-service trainings on Values Education content, instruction, assessment and materials/resources affects quality of teaching	3.37	Strongly Agree	7
8. Teacher fails to encourage their students' commitment to Filipino dominant and core values	3.35	Strongly Agree	9
9. Limited content knowledge on Values education because teachers are non-Values education major.	3.35	Strongly Agree	9
10. Lack of planning of activities due to time constraints.	3.38	Strongly Agree	5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.38	Strongly Agree	

The overall weighted mean on the difficulties in teaching values education as to Content/Teaching domains was 3.38 with qualitative interpretation of "Strongly Agree". The teacher-respondents strongly agreed that having limited learning activities aimed to develop students' personal values, group values and societal values was the most identified difficulties in teaching Values Education as to Content/Teaching domains.

Table 8: Difficulties in Teaching Values Education in terms of Strategies

Strategies	Mean	QI	Rank
1. Lack of trainings and seminars for non-values education major among teachers.	3.40	Strongly Agree	8
2. Lack of classroom teaching gadgets.	3.44	Strongly Agree	1.5
3. Lack of Professional development support when it comes to enjoying classroom management strategies.	3.43	Strongly Agree	3.5
4. Teacher's difficulty in using variety of strategies that will create positive environment and active participation among students especially technology experiences.	3.41	Strongly Agree	7
5. Limited time allotment for the subject values education.	3.44	Strongly Agree	1.5
6. Teacher's struggling to determine appropriate strategies due to specific teacher's guidelines.	3.42	Strongly Agree	5.5
7. Difficulty on the teacher's role as model to instill values to their students.	3.42	Strongly Agree	5.5
8. Student's sensitivity to their rights and beliefs.	3.38	Strongly Agree	9
9. Time allotment to make collaborative, home visits with parents to ensure effectiveness of values education.	3.35	Strongly Agree	10
10. Setting high level of experiences which will facilitated to the upbringing of character development in their own lives.	3.43	Strongly Agree	3.5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.41	Strongly Agree	

The overall weighted mean on the difficulties in teaching values education as to Strategies was 3.41 with qualitative interpretation of “Strongly Agree”. The teacher-respondents strongly agreed that lack of classroom teaching gadgets for presenting lessons in Values Education was the main problem identified difficulties in teaching. Instructional materials, resources, and technology are very much needed and valued by teachers in Values Education of the present study.

Table 9: Difficulties in Teaching Values Education in terms of Assessment

Assessment	Mean	QI	Rank
1. Limited knowledge on the changes in formative and summative assessment tools and techniques	3.40	Strongly Agree	1
2. Limited knowledge on the administration of formative and summative assessments through synchronous and asynchronous forms	3.39	Strongly Agree	3
3. Not being able to assess of students’ products (processes and performances) through synchronous and asynchronous forms	3.39	Strongly Agree	3
4. Not being able to assess students’ performance and authentic output appropriately	3.39	Strongly Agree	3
5. Not knowing how to prepare to rubric not being able to find prepared rubric	3.38	Strongly Agree	5
6. Not being able to assess objectively and giving undeserved notes to the students	3.37	Strongly Agree	6.5
7. Teachers have limited strategies for timely, accurate and constructive feedback to learners to improve learning.	3.37	Strongly Agree	6.5
8. Teachers have difficulty keeping individual records of students necessary in the making of final rating and evaluation	3.36	Strongly Agree	9
9. Teachers have limited strategies for effective and reporting to parents/guardians about students’ progress	3.36	Strongly Agree	9
10. Teachers lack proper training on new trends in assessment tools and technique appropriate for teaching Values Education	3.36	Strongly Agree	9
Overall Weighted Mean	3.38	Strongly Agree	

Overall, the computed mean of the responses towards difficulties in teaching values education as to Assessment was 3.38 with qualitative interpretation of “Strongly Agree”.

Academic Performance of the Junior High School Students in Values Education

Table 10: Distribution on the Academic Performance of the Junior High School Students in Values Education

Academic Performance	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Satisfactory (80-84)	2	0.70
Very Satisfactory (85-89)	14	4.70
Outstanding (90-100)	284	94.70
Total	300	100.00
Mean of Academic Performance =94.54 (Outstanding)		

There were 2 (0.70%) students who gained a grade ranging from 80-84 with interpretation of Satisfactory; 14 (4.70%) students whose grade was 85-89 with interpretation of Very Satisfactory; overwhelming figure of 284 (94.70%) students gained a rating of 90-100 with

qualitative description of Outstanding. The mean of academic performance =94.54 with descriptive remarks of Outstanding. The performance of the students in Values Education was exemplary supported with their mean grade of 94.54.

Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment on the Use of Strategies and Approaches in Teaching Values Education according to their Profile Variables

Table 11: Test of Difference on the Use of Strategies and Approaches in Teaching Values Education in terms of Inculcation Approach when grouped according to Profile Variables

Sources of Variations		SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	Decision
Sex	Between Groups	0.060	1	0.060	0.324	0.570	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	55.514	298	0.186			
	Total	55.574	299				
Age	Between Groups	2.408	5	0.482	2.664	0.023	Reject Ho Significant
	Within Groups	53.166	294	0.181			
	Total	55.574	299				
Years in Teaching Values Education	Between Groups	1.564	4	0.391	2.136	0.076	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	54.010	295	0.183			
	Total	55.574	299				
No. of trainings in Moral Education/ Values Education	Between Groups	0.520	3	0.173	0.932	0.425	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	55.054	296	0.186			
	Total	55.574	299				
Religious Affiliation	Between Groups	3.031	5	0.606	3.392	0.005	Reject Ho Significant
	Within Groups	52.543	294	0.179			
	Total	55.574	299				
Civil Status	Between Groups	0.871	4	0.218	1.174	0.322	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	54.703	295	0.185			
	Total	55.574	299				

The computed Sig. Values of 0.023 and 0.005 for the use of teaching strategies and approach are lower than (<) 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, null hypothesis is rejected, hence there is significant difference on the use of strategies and approaches in teaching values education when grouped according to age and religious affiliation respectively.

The teacher – respondents who vary in terms of age and religious affiliation show likeness of knowledge and skill in the utilization of Inculcation Approach in teaching Values Education.

Table 12: Test of Difference on the Use of Strategies and Approaches in Teaching Values Education in terms of Awareness Approach when grouped according to Profile Variables

Sources of Variations		SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	Decision
Sex	Between Groups	0.220	1	0.220	1.258	0.263	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	52.081	298	0.175			
	Total	52.301	299				
Age	Between Groups	2.628	5	0.526	3.110	0.009	Reject Ho Significant
	Within Groups	49.673	294	0.169			
	Total	52.301	299				
Years in Teaching Values Education	Between Groups	0.907	4	0.227	1.302	0.269	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	51.394	295	0.174			
	Total	52.301	299				
No. of trainings in Moral Education/Values Education	Between Groups	0.381	3	0.127	0.724	0.538	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	51.920	296	0.175			
	Total	52.301	299				
Religious Affiliation	Between Groups	0.845	5	0.169	0.966	0.439	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	51.456	294	0.175			
	Total	52.301	299				
Civil Status	Between Groups	0.452	4	0.113	0.642	0.633	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	51.849	295	0.176			
	Total	52.301	299				

The computed Sig. Value of 0.009 which is lower than (<) 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, null hypothesis is rejected, hence there is significant difference on the use of strategies and approaches in teaching values education when grouped according to age. The teacher – respondents who vary in terms of age show likeness of knowledge and skill in the utilization of Awareness Approach in teaching Values Education.

Table 13: Test of Difference on the Use of Strategies and Approaches in Teaching Values Education in terms of Moral Reasoning Approach when grouped according to Profile Variables

Sources of Variations		SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	Decision
Sex	Between Groups	0.001	1	0.001	0.008	0.927	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	50.554	298	0.170			
	Total	50.555	299				
Age	Between Groups	1.290	5	0.258	1.539	0.177	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	49.266	294	0.168			
	Total	50.555	299				
Years in Teaching Values Education	Between Groups	0.827	4	0.207	1.226	0.300	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	49.728	295	0.169			
	Total	50.555	299				
No. of trainings in Moral Education/Values Education	Between Groups	0.401	3	0.134	0.789	0.501	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	50.154	296	0.169			
	Total	50.555	299				
Religious Affiliation	Between Groups	1.224	5	0.245	1.458	0.203	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	49.332	294	0.168			
	Total	50.555	299				
Civil Status	Between Groups	0.625	4	0.156	0.923	0.451	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	49.931	295	0.169			
	Total	50.555	299				

There is no significant difference on the use of strategies and approaches in teaching values education as to Moral Reasoning approach when grouped according to profile variables, hence the null hypothesis is accepted

Table 14: Test of Difference on the Use of Strategies and Approaches in Teaching Values Education in terms of Value Clarification Approach when grouped according to Profile Variables

Sources of Variations		SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	Decision
Sex	Between Groups	0.000	1	0.000	0.000	0.993	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	51.730	298	0.174			
	Total	51.730	299				
Age	Between Groups	0.799	5	0.160	0.922	0.467	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	50.931	294	0.173			
	Total	51.730	299				
Years in Teaching Values Education	Between Groups	0.961	4	0.240	1.396	0.235	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	50.769	295	0.172			
	Total	51.730	299				
No. of trainings in Moral Education/ Values Education	Between Groups	0.675	3	0.225	1.304	0.273	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	51.055	296	0.172			
	Total	51.730	299				
Religious Affiliation	Between Groups	0.242	5	0.048	0.276	0.926	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	51.488	294	0.175			
	Total	51.730	299				
Civil Status	Between Groups	0.207	4	0.052	0.296	0.880	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	51.523	295	0.175			
	Total	51.730	299				

There is no significant difference on the use of strategies and approaches in teaching values education as to Value clarification approach when grouped according to profile variables, hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 15: Test of Difference on the Use of Strategies and Approaches in Teaching Values Education in terms of Evocation Approach when grouped according to Profile Variables

Sources of Variations		SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	Decision
Sex	Between Groups	0.030	1	0.030	0.180	0.672	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	48.871	298	0.164			
	Total	48.900	299				
Age	Between Groups	1.715	5	0.343	2.138	0.061	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	47.185	294	0.160			
	Total	48.900	299				
Years in Teaching Values Education	Between Groups	0.032	4	0.008	0.049	0.996	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	48.868	295	0.166			
	Total	48.900	299				
No. of trainings in Moral Education/ Values Education	Between Groups	0.088	3	0.029	0.177	0.912	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	48.813	296	0.165			
	Total	48.900	299				
Religious Affiliation	Between Groups	0.224	5	0.045	0.270	0.929	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	48.677	294	0.166			
	Total	48.900	299				
Civil Status	Between Groups	0.549	4	0.137	0.837	0.502	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	48.351	295	0.164			
	Total	48.900	299				

There is no significant difference on the use of strategies and approaches in teaching values education as to Evocation approach when grouped according to profile variables, hence the null hypothesis is accepted

Test of Significant Difference on the Difficulties in Teaching Values Education according to their Profile Variables

Table 16: Test of Difference on the Difficulties in Teaching Values Education in terms of Content/Teaching Domains when grouped according to Profile Variables

Sources of Variations		SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	Decision
Sex	Between Groups	0.002	1	0.002	0.013	0.910	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	44.075	298	0.148			
	Total	44.077	299				
Age	Between Groups	2.026	5	0.405	2.833	0.016	Reject Ho Significant
	Within Groups	42.050	294	0.143			
	Total	44.077	299				
Years in Teaching Values Education	Between Groups	0.287	4	0.072	0.483	0.748	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	43.790	295	0.148			
	Total	44.077	299				
No. of trainings in Moral Education/ Values Education	Between Groups	0.366	3	0.122	0.826	0.481	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	43.711	296	0.148			
	Total	44.077	299				
Religious Affiliation	Between Groups	0.462	5	0.092	0.623	0.682	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	43.614	294	0.148			
	Total	44.077	299				
Civil Status	Between Groups	0.617	4	0.154	1.048	0.383	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	43.459	295	0.147			
	Total	44.077	299				

The computed Sig. Values of 0.016 which is lower than (<) 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, null hypothesis is rejected, hence there is significant difference on the use of strategies and approaches in teaching values education when grouped according to age.

The Values Education teachers who varies in terms of age (younger and adult) have different perception on Content/Teaching Domains difficulties in teaching Values Education.

Table 17: Test of Difference on the Difficulties in Teaching Values Education in terms of Strategies when grouped according to Profile Variables

Sources of Variations		SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	Decision
Sex	Between Groups	0.007	1	0.007	0.042	0.838	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	47.475	298	0.159			
	Total	47.481	299				
Age	Between Groups	1.510	5	0.302	1.931	0.089	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	45.972	294	0.156			
	Total	47.481	299				
Years in Teaching Values Education	Between Groups	0.719	4	0.180	1.133	0.341	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	46.763	295	0.159			
	Total	47.481	299				
No. of trainings in Moral Education/Values Education	Between Groups	0.192	3	0.064	0.401	0.752	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	47.289	296	0.160			
	Total	47.481	299				
Religious Affiliation	Between Groups	0.783	5	0.157	0.985	0.427	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	46.699	294	0.159			
	Total	47.481	299				
Civil Status	Between Groups	0.307	4	0.077	0.480	0.751	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	47.175	295	0.160			
	Total	47.481	299				

There is no significant difference on the on the difficulties in teaching values education as described by the teachers as to Strategies when grouped according to profile variables, hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 18: Test of Difference on the Difficulties in Teaching Values Education in terms of Assessment when grouped according to Profile Variables

Sources of Variations		SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	Decision
Sex	Between Groups	0.056	1	0.056	0.357	0.551	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	46.926	298	0.157			
	Total	46.982	299				
Age	Between Groups	1.641	5	0.328	2.128	0.062	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	45.341	294	0.154			
	Total	46.982	299				
Years in Teaching Values Education	Between Groups	0.517	4	0.129	0.821	0.513	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	46.465	295	0.158			
	Total	46.982	299				
No. of trainings in Moral Education/Values Education	Between Groups	0.098	3	0.033	0.207	0.892	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	46.884	296	0.158			
	Total	46.982	299				
Religious Affiliation	Between Groups	0.606	5	0.121	0.768	0.573	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	46.376	294	0.158			
	Total	46.982	299				
Civil Status	Between Groups	0.156	4	0.039	0.245	0.913	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	46.826	295	0.159			
	Total	46.982	299				

There is no significant difference on the on the difficulties in teaching values education as described by the teachers as to Assessment when grouped according to profile variables, hence the null hypothesis is accepted

Test of Significant Relationship in terms of Effectiveness of Strategies and Approaches, Difficulties and the Academic Performance of the Students

Table 19: Test of Relationship between in terms of Effectiveness of Strategies and Approaches Difficulties and the Academic Performance of the Students

Sources of Correlations		Academic Performance of the Students
Effectiveness of Strategies and Approaches Used	Pearson Correlation	0.018
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.762
	N	300
Difficulties in Teaching Values Education	Pearson Correlation	0.057
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.328
	N	300

There is negligible correlation between the effectiveness of strategies and approaches and the academic performance of the students manifested on the computed Pearson r –value of 0.018. The computed Sig. (2-tailed) value of 0.762; and negligible correlation between the difficulties in teaching values education, manifested on the computed Pearson r –value of 0.057, which are higher than 5% significant level, the null hypothesis is accepted.

CONCLUSIONS

The teachers always used Inculcation Approach as strategy in teaching Values Education. Inculcation Approach was very much effective among the approaches in teaching Values Education. The respondents strongly agreed that the strategies in teaching Values Education was the most difficult dimension in teaching Values Education.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The researcher recommended that head teachers and teachers in Values Education should make innovations on how Inculcation Approach in teaching the subject be more useful and effective. Head Teachers, Principals, Education Specialist on Values Education of Division of Zambales may focus their In-service Trainings ways how teachers enhance the utilization and effectiveness of approaches such as Moral Reasoning, Awareness.

Value Clarification and Evocation. The teachers should look and utilize suitable techniques for Inculcation, Moral Reasoning, Awareness, Value Clarification and Evocation approaches such as role playing, group dynamics and simulations and learning activities that would develop personal values, group values and societal values.

Head Teachers and teachers are encouraged to attend national and international trainings and seminars for better understanding and improved skill in selecting appropriate strategies, on the development of learning content and assessment procedures in Values Education.

A training design was formulated to address the challenges encountered by Multi-Grade Values Education Teachers

INTERVENTION PROGRAM TO ADDRESS THE CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED BY MULTI-GRADE VALUES EDUCATION TEACHERS

KEY AREA	OBJECTIVE/S	SPECIFIC ACTIVITIES	OUTPUTS	Person(s) Involved	Proposed Budget
Approaches / Strategies in Teaching Values Education	<p>Improved utilization of Values Education pedagogies with resilience and tolerance of students' diversity; communication and research skills; and help develop students' social skills.</p> <p>Explore relevant techniques of Values Education approaches specifically focused on students' wellbeing, respect and responsibility.</p> <p>Design/plan and execute Values Education learning tasks and activities utilizing different approaches for further understanding and learning of Values Education contents/ lessons.</p> <p>Consider and employ the opportunity to integrate</p>	<p>Activities: Conduct and/or participation in In-Service Trainings, Seminars, Workshops.</p> <p>Conduct of Learning Action Cell (LAC) Sessions</p> <p>Participation in Project Group and/or Professional Group Discussions</p> <p>Suggested Topics: "Best Practices in Inculcation, Awareness, Moral Reasoning, Value Clarification and Evocation Approaches in Values Education Program"</p> <p>"Efficacy of Techniques toward Values Education, Moral Development and</p>	<p>Expected Outputs: Innovative Approach/Strategy in Values Education</p> <p>Strategic Intervention Materials for Values Education</p> <p>Module/ Worksheets/ Simple Handout or Handbook for Values Education</p> <p>Research Proposal / Research Output related to Values Education</p>	<p>School Head</p> <p>Department Head</p> <p>Lecturers/ Resource Persons</p> <p>Teacher/s</p> <p>Students</p>	<p>Php 45,000.00</p>

	<p>Values Education lessons - interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary.</p> <p>Utilize Values Education approaches and strategies for developing students' critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills and for improved classroom communication.</p>	<p>Civic and Citizenship Education”</p> <p>“Engaging Learning Tasks and Activities in Values Education Teaching”</p> <p>“Interdisciplinary and Multidisciplinary Teaching of Values Education”</p> <p>“Values Education Approaches towards Critical and Creative Thinking, and HOT”</p>			
KEY AREA	OBJECTIVE/S	SPECIFIC ACTIVITIES	OUTPUTS	Person(s) Involved	Proposed Budget
<p>Values Education Contents and Learning Competencies</p>	<p>Considers and respects diversity that emanates from factors such as gender, religious beliefs, family values and practices in presenting Values Education contents.</p> <p>Renew attention and emphasis on the importance of citizenship, growing nationalism and environmental awareness.</p>	<p>Activities:</p> <p>Conduct and/or participation in In-Service Trainings, Seminars, Workshops.</p> <p>Conduct of Learning Action Cell (LAC) Sessions</p> <p>Participation in Project Group and/or Professional Group Discussions</p> <p>Suggested Topics:</p>	<p>Expected Outputs:</p> <p>Strategic Intervention Materials for Values Education</p> <p>Module/ Worksheets/ Simple Handout or Handbook for Values Education</p> <p>Research Proposal /</p>	<p>School Head</p> <p>Department Head</p> <p>Lecturers/ Resource Persons</p> <p>Teacher/s</p> <p>Students</p>	<p>Php 55,000.00</p>
	<p>Ensure autonomy and freedom among teachers to improve and modify their own modules in Values Education based from evaluations and students' needs.</p> <p>Identify specific expectations or learning outcomes in Values Education using the Curriculum Guide/MELCs.</p> <p>Organize purposeful and engaging learning experiences and activities in teaching Values Education contents.</p> <p>Organize Values Education lessons aimed to develop students' personal values, group values and societal values</p> <p>Plan, review, and continuously adjust on what works, what didn't, and how to improve teaching Values Education.</p>	<p>“Stating Deeper and Measurable Objectives on Values Education Lessons Based on Curriculum Guide/ MELCs”</p> <p>“Students' Diversity and Values Education Program”</p> <p>“Values Education, Civic Consciousness and Citizenship Education”</p> <p>“Relevance of Values Education in the 21st Century”</p> <p>“Trends and Issues during the Pandemic as Values Education Contents”</p> <p>“Application and Utilization of Efficient and Effective Instructional Planning in Values Education”</p> <p>“Best Practices on Instructional Planning and Lesson Preparation in Values Education”</p>	<p>Research Output related to Values Education</p>		

KEY AREA	OBJECTIVE/S	SPECIFIC ACTIVITIES	OUTPUTS	Person(s) Involved	Proposed Budget
	Evaluate the quality of available resources when designing a unit or lesson in Values Education.				
Values Education Assessment Techniques & Tools	<p>Demonstrate knowledge in designing, selecting and preparation of diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies for Values Education curriculum requirements.</p> <p>Improved utilization of assessment strategies through synchronous and asynchronous forms.</p> <p>Assess students' performances and authentic outputs in Values Education appropriately.</p> <p>Use of assessment data to enhance teaching and learning practices in Values Education Programs.</p> <p>Master the process of interpretation of data to help</p>	<p>Activities: Conduct and/or participation in In-Service Trainings, Seminars, Workshops.</p> <p>Conduct of Learning Action Cell (LAC) Sessions</p> <p>Participation in Project Group and/or Professional Group Discussions</p> <p>Suggested Topics: "Learning Assessment Challenges in Values Education Program during the COVID19 Pandemic" "Diagnostic, Formative and Summative Assessment Strategies and Learning Modules in Values Education"</p>	<p>Expected Outputs: Strategic Intervention Materials for Values Education</p> <p>Module/ Worksheets/ Simple Handout or Handbook for Values Education</p> <p>Compilation of Assessment Tools for Values Education</p> <p>Research Proposal / Research Output related to Values Education</p>	<p>School Head</p> <p>Department Head</p> <p>Lecturers/ Resource Persons</p> <p>Teacher/s</p> <p>Students</p>	<p>Php 57,000.00</p>
	<p>make better decisions regarding evaluation of learner' progress in Values Education</p> <p>Communication and reporting of learner needs, progress and achievement to parents</p>	<p>"Monitoring and Reporting of Students' Progress during the Pandemic - Synchronous and Asynchronous Forms"</p> <p>"Designing, Preparing and Utilization of Alternative Assessment (Performance-Based and Authentic) Tools in Values Education"</p> <p>"Application/Utilization of Accumulated Assessment Process to Students"</p>			

References

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- 5) Ryan, L. 2016). Values and teaching. (2nd. ed.) Columbus: Charles E. Merrill Publishing Company